

Wind and PV Energy Production

An Evaluation of the Production Forecasts in Germany

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ABSTRACT

The share of electricity from renewable energies in the total electricity supply in Germany has increased significantly in recent years. In 2015, electric power from renewable energies had a share of approx. 30 % of gross electricity generation. Of this, the supply-dependent feed-in from wind energy and photovoltaic (PV) plants had the largest share of generation from renewables at 63%. [1]

This electricity generation, which is strongly influenced by local weather conditions, is partly characterized by considerable fluctuations, but above all by its partly still poor predictability. According to the current legal requirements, the feed-in of electricity from renewable energies is preferred. In order to cover the remaining residual load, which often fluctuates strongly, and to compensate for the forecast errors that occur, the need for flexible generators and consumers in the system increases disproportionately with the increase in feed-in, so that the usual high level of supply security in the German electricity system can be guaranteed at all times. Thus, the forecast quality of the weather-dependent feed-in and its reliability determine the demand for balancing energy in the power supply system to a considerable extent. A reliable power forecast of the weather-dependent feed-in over the next few hours is decisive for the optimal deployment planning of the various power generators and selected consumers in the supply system with regard to technical, economic and ecological criteria. The respective forecast horizon is mainly determined by the general conditions of the energy industry; for example, short-term forecasts are sufficient for resource planning on the day-ahead or intra-day market, whereas longer-term forecasts must be made for the balancing power market. The forecast quality is significantly influenced by the forecast horizon.

In the future, a further increase of wind and PV power can be assumed. With a further preferential feed-in of electricity from fluctuating renewable energies, further increasing gradients of the residual load and thus an increased demand for balancing energy is to be expected. This will also place increased demands on the conventional power plant fleet, which will have to react even more directly to changes in the residual load in the intra-day market and to maintain balancing energy in the system. In addition, a further increase in wind and solar generation - with hardly any increase in demand - will result in an increasing displacement of the conventional power plant park, so that generators based on fluctuating renewable energies - as well as flexible consumers - will also have to contribute to the provision of balancing energy.[2] In order to be able to estimate the given balancing power potential of such weather-dependent generation

plants under these conditions, it must be known which time- and location-dependent part of the feed-in forecast is reliable, so that an overestimation of the real wind supply can be excluded with a defined reliability.

Against this background, the aim of the following explanations is to analyze the day-ahead forecast quality of the feed-in from wind energy and PV plants in the control areas of the German transmission system operators (TSOs, in German "ÜNB Übertragungsnetzbetreiber") and for the entire area of Germany for the years 2010 to 2015. This will allow the impact of weather-dependent power generation from wind and solar on the electricity system to be assessed.

KEYWORDS

Data science, photovoltaic, wind, renewables, energy, prediction

METHODS

The day-ahead power forecast is currently prepared at 8 a.m. for every quarter of an hour for the entire following day by various forecasting institutes on behalf of the TSOs. This results in a forecast horizon of the forecast feed-in of 16 to 40 h.[3]

This short-term forecast is based, among other things, on meteorological parameters predicted by one or more independent numerical weather models, which are linked with the regionally distributed plant capacity and the measured feed-in values of generation plants using statistical methods. Numerical weather forecasts are usually characterized by inaccurate initial conditions, simplified topography, and a fuzzy description of physical and dynamic processes; in addition, there is the fundamentally chaotic behavior of the atmosphere. In particular, strong abrupt changes in wind speed or global radiation due to fog and snow situations are difficult to predict.[4] Therefore, this prediction is still subject to considerable uncertainties. Within the examined years, significant improvements of energy prediction models have been achieved by using high-resolution model calculations, ensemble predictions (meta-forecasts) and online corrections based on actual values; this is especially true for wind power prediction. Nevertheless, the quality of the power forecast is largely determined by the quality of the weather forecast, and the selection of the weather model - and thus, among other things, its model resolution, its original objective, and its intended adaptation to specific site conditions - has a significant influence on the forecast quality.[5] However, the concrete bases and assumptions of the available weather

models are generally not publicly available or only to a limited extent.

The forecast error data is provided by the German TSO's TransnetBW, Amprion, 50Hertz and Tennet.[6] [7] [8] [9] In the following, parameters and reference values for the description of the forecast uncertainties are presented and their application for the evaluation of the dependencies of the forecast quality is methodically explained.

FORECAST EVALUATION

From a statistical point of view, the forecast of wind or PV feed-in can be understood as an estimate. The forecast error X results from the difference between the feed-in forecast P_r and the projections of the actual feed-in data I for each point in time ($X = P_r - I$). Positive forecast errors thus mean an overestimation, negative ones an underestimation of the real wind or PV supply. The forecast quality and thus the quality of the estimation procedure can be characterized by the following parameters.

- Minimum and maximum forecast errors X_{min}/X_{max} . These parameters are only aimed at a singular event and therefore have only a limited statistical significance for the forecast quality. They indicate a minimum or maximum event occurring at due time in the study period and are in no way to be understood as an upper or lower limit of the errors.[5]
- Arithmetic mean M . It describes the bias of the power forecast P_r from the actual value I and is used to assess whether the wind or PV supply is overestimated or underestimated on average for the number of samples N (eq. 1). The bias describes the expectation fidelity of an estimator.[10]

$$M = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (X_i) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (P_{r_i} - I_i) \quad (1)$$

- Root Mean Squared Error $RMSE$. The $RMSE$ indicates the spread of the forecast errors and is therefore a measure of the accuracy of the estimator. The $RMSE$ is the decisive parameter for the assessment of forecast quality, since it takes systematic and random errors into account. It can therefore also be expressed by the arithmetic mean M and the variance VAR (Eq. 2). The quadratic approach also gives greater weight to larger errors and thus better approximates potential economic consequences for the electricity system.[5]

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (X_i)^2} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (P_{r_i} - I_i)^2} = \sqrt{VAR + M^2} \quad (2)$$

RESULTS WIND POWER

Minimum and maximum error: Above all, the maximum errors have fallen in recent years - despite increasing installed system

output. Average extreme minimum of the forecast errors is -25% while the average extreme maximum error is +19% of the total power capacity.

Arithmetic mean: With a mean of 106 Megawatt, this parameter is predominantly positive. This positive bias of the real wind supply by the forecast results in an increased demand for positive control power. In relation to the installed wind power, this bias is very small.

RMSE: With an average of 1154 Megawatt (3,7% of the total power capacity), the average RMSE of the wind feed-in shows that the random error has a significantly higher influence on the forecast quality than the systematic bias. Between 2010 and 2015, an improvement of the forecast quality of the wind feed-in by about 19% can be seen. In this context, 2015 represents a year with low forecast quality in comparison. In the years 2007 to 10, the forecast quality of the wind feed-in could be increased.[11]

RESULTS PV POWER

Minimum and maximum error: The maximum errors are -17% and +22% of the total power capacity and therefore rather similar to the extreme values in wind power forecasts.

Arithmetic mean: With a mean of 57 Megawatt, the bias for PV power production is - not unlike forecast for wind power - positive. However, the bias in relation to the installed potential is very low again.

RMSE: With an average of 1260 Megawatt (3,6% of the total power capacity), the forecast quality of the PV feed-in averaged over the examined years shows that the forecast inaccuracy is also mainly caused by random errors. In the case of PV feed-in, only slightly pronounced tendencies in the development of the forecast quality are recognizable. However, there is no deterioration of the forecast despite increasing installed capacity.

With an average of 1260 Megawatt (3,6% of the total power capacity), the average RMSE of the wind feed-in shows that the random error has a significantly higher influence on the forecast quality than the systematic bias. Between 2010 and 2015, an improvement of the forecast quality of the wind feed-in by about 19% can be seen. In this context, 2015 represents a year with low forecast quality in comparison. In the years 2007 to 10, the forecast quality of the wind feed-in could be increased.[11]

CONCLUSIONS

In the future, the electrical energy supply will be characterized by a further increase in the share of power generation from weather-dependent energies. In order to integrate this power generation into a secure power supply system at optimal costs, reliable forecasts of the wind and solar power generation to be expected in the coming hours and days will become increasingly important. For this reason, the aim of this study is to examine in detail the forecast quality of the wind and PV power feed-in for Germany for the years 2010 to 2015, and thus to make a statement as to what proportion of the wind and PV power forecast for the

following day can be regarded as reliably predictable. The increase of the reliably predictable power shall be quantified by a higher level of detail in the mapping of the forecast error. Overall, we can conclude that random errors have a higher impact than systemic biases.

Due to availability of literature, this study examined the years 2010 to 2015. An examination of more recent years should be done to determine whether and how the forecast quality has changed. Also, in further studies different factors and their impact on forecast error should be examined. For example, which impact do seasonal differences have on forecast errors? Are forecasts in summer different than forecasts in winter? Are there regional differences? Also, a comparison of forecast quality based on the used weather models should be looked at.

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